

HOW CAN WE SPEAK NATURALLY LIKE A NATIVE SPEAKER?

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Abstract:

Learning foreign languages can be exciting and enjoyable moment, however, it requires so much time and effort to be good at, especially, in communication. Even through they know the grammar and have enough vocabulary learners can not communicate with each other due to hesitation or fear. There is a number strategy that can help to improve their speaking skills. Everybody can choose strategies according to their interest and abilities, they can get satisfaction from the learning process along the way helps to manage their time. Thus, teachers should direct average students' interests in the right direction. If the learners have a passionate to improve language skills, they can make time for working on their own and will be successful in this field.

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Here are some effective speaking strategies teachers encourage their students to speak naturally. One of the most common strategy is among learners is shadowing technique. Arguelles defines shadowing as a language learning technique where the students listens to a recording of target language audio, and simultaneously echoes what they hear. Shadowing is designed to force you to focus on the sounds of your target language and develop pronunciation that mimics a native speaker. Arguelles recommends doing repeating aloud in a loud, articulate manner, while shadowing, because it helps to improve your focus and memory. Moreover, shadowing allows the listener to hear everything twice, providing more natural weight to the utterance from hearing and producing it. Kadota (2012) introduces two types of shadowing: pre-shadowing (shadowing before learning the lesson content) and post-shadowing (shadowing after learning the lesson content). In pre-shadowing, learners can deliberately focus on the incoming sounds because those sounds comprise the only information on which they can rely. In post-shadowing, being familiar with the target passage can ease learners' anxiety (Hamada, 2011b), which consequently lowers the psychological costs of shadowing. Against this background, the author was interested to explore whether shadowing is an effective technique to use in teaching receptive skills, through studying learners' improvement in producing the correct stress by using this technique.

The shadowing technique works best for a few types of people:

- Auditory learners
- Students who learn best with structured study plans
- Polyglots

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Even if you do not fall into one of those groups, this out-of-the-box learning method can help energize your same old, same old study plan. Plus, the focused pronunciation practice is inherently valuable, especially if you do not have lots of other opportunities for target language speaking practice.

So with language shadowing, our intonation develops as we listen and repeat, the same way it does with our native language. Both accents and intonation are crucial to achieving language fluency, so you sound of much more natural when you speak, instead of like you are reading from a textbook.

Of course, there are many different ways to approach learning a new language, and shadowing does not work everyone. Like any other method, your individual success with shadowing is dependent on how much time, effort and dedication you put into it.

Shadowing is a very successful and useful language learning method when applied correctly. Linguists analyzed different stages of language shadowing.

You should use the shadowing technique in the following order to develop your speaking skills:

1. Choose your Audio Resource

Before you choose an audio resource, there are a number of factors you should consider:

It is important to consider your language level. If your source is too advanced or too easy, the shadowing technique may be less effective.

You will also want to make sure your audio resource has a text component with an English translation (for example, an e-book version of your audiobook in both languages) You will see why in the steps below.

Videos featuring native speakers are also highly useful for shadowing because you get to see the language being used in context, which helps you remember the meanings faster. Whatever resource you choose, you will want to make sure it is convenient to use and plentiful in content.

2. Practice in your native language first

To ease yourself into the method, try it with a recording of yourself in English or your native language.

Read a text aloud, slightly slower than normal, for two or three minutes. Then play back the recording and try to repeat after it. You do not want to wait for a sentence or even a word to end before repeating it your repetitions should be as close to simultaneous with the recording as possible.

This will get you accustomed to the slightly unusual feeling of speaking and listening at the same time. Now you are ready to try it with a foreign language.

3. Just listen and focus on the sounds

Listen to the dialogue in your target language with headphones or earbuds a couple of times without reading any transcript or speaking aloud. Focus on the sound and feel the words in your mind, even if you do not have a clue what they actually mean.

The most important part of this step is to acknowledge and focus on the target language before you move on the next stage.

4. Listen and repeat while walking around

An unconventional but critical part of language shadowing is walking around while listening to and repeating your audio resource.

Walking or pacing while shadowing will seem uncomfortable at first, especially since many of us are inclined to sit down while studying. But as you keep going it will become easier and more natural.

5. Listen and repeat while reading the English Translation

Now you can start learning what you have actually been saying this whole time! Go back to the start of your passage and shadow while reading the English translation of your book or transcript. As Arguelles puts, it this will give you “global” understanding of what you are listening to and saying. You will start to associate meaning with the target language sounds in a natural way.

Well as Again, repeat this stage several times. While you might want to stop pacing around for your own safety, Arguelles still recommends holding your text out in front of you rather than at your lap and keeping an upright posture.

Another important strategy is communicating with native speakers as much as possible.

Nowadays Internet offers a number of programs that helps to find and communicate with foreigners. We can use them whenever we need to improve our language skills.

Some programs are divided into special levels everyone can choose according to their level, as a result it would be better approach to their communication develop.

To be more precise, native speakers can find our weakness and mistakes during communication and provide suitable solutions to overcome difficulties in speaking process. Mainly sharing ideas with them helps to broaden our subconscious horizon, which makes us perfect speakers. Furthermore, there are different sites like Duo lingo, kayoed they help to check our speaking skills as making the process much easier to follow. This app can maintain every individual accents and pronunciation, by doing so they can avoid making grammatic mistakes.

Reading books play significant role not only enhancing our vocabulary but also speaking. For example, from reading so many books and articles we can get a new idea and learn grammar or sentence structure. After reading books and articles learner can retell what they understood from the plot, which leads to advancements in speaking part.

Even through having a lot of strategies and approaches to develop our language learning skills choosing one suitable depends on learner and their interests. Retelling the stories and shadowing can be useful for people having certain levels, particularly, these methods should be applied Pre-Intermediate and Intermediate levels. As they have gained a lot of back ground knowledge comprehending the plot of the stories, they don't deal with difficulties while they are developing the way that they communicate.

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